

Comparative Analysis of Healing Duration after Modified Radical Mastoidectomy with and Without Mastoid Cavity Obliteration

Piyush Prakash¹, Sanjeet Kumar Goit², Amit Sharma³¹Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Madhubani Medical College, Madhubani, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India³Associate Professor, Department of ENT, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 18-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sanjeet Kumar Goit

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is a persistent inflammatory condition of the middle ear that often requires surgical intervention, such as Modified Radical Mastoidectomy MRM. Postoperative healing of the mastoid cavity can be prolonged, leading to complications. Mastoid Cavity Obliteration MCO has been proposed as a technique to accelerate healing and reduce complications.

Aim: This study aims to compare the healing time and postoperative outcomes between patients undergoing MRM with and without mastoid cavity obliteration MCO.

Methods: A study was conducted over six months involving 104 participants. Participants were divided into two groups: those who underwent MRM with MCO (Group A) and those without obliteration (Group B). Healing time, defined as the period until complete epithelization of the mastoid cavity, was the primary outcome. Secondary outcomes included postoperative complications. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with independent samples t-tests and multivariate regression analysis.

Results: Group A showed significantly faster healing times, with an average of 6.8 weeks compared to 9.2 weeks in Group B ($p < 0.001$). Multivariate regression analysis confirmed that obliteration was an independent predictor of reduced healing time. Although the incidence of postoperative complications was lower in Group A, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.22$).

Conclusion: Mastoid Cavity Obliteration MCO significantly accelerates healing time following MRM and may reduce postoperative complications. These findings support the routine use of MCO in eligible patients to improve surgical outcomes.

Recommendations: Further research with a larger sample size and longer follow-up is recommended to confirm these findings and assess the long-term benefits and risks of mastoid cavity obliteration.

Keywords: Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media, Modified Radical Mastoidectomy, Mastoid Cavity Obliteration, Healing Time, Postoperative Complications.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is characterised by recurrent ear discharge through a perforated tympanic membrane. Because of its link to hearing loss, recurring infections, and potentially fatal consequences such as intracranial infections and facial nerve paralysis, it is a serious health issue, especially in impoverished nations [1, 2]. To end the condition and stop its consequences, surgery, such as MRM, is still the major therapeutic option for CSOM [3].

MRM aims to preserve as much of the natural structure as feasible while eliminating illness from the middle ear and mastoid. Nonetheless, the healing of the mastoid cavity following surgery is one of the main difficulties with this operation. Prolonged and complex healing can result in long-

term dental problems, repeated infections, and lifetime aural care requirements [4]. MCO has been presented as an auxiliary to MRM in order to solve these difficulties. In order to minimise surgical problems, accelerate healing, and reduce cavity size, this approach includes filling the mastoid cavity with synthetic or autologous materials [5].

Promising findings from recent research indicate that MCO might have advantages. For example, a research showed that patients who had MCO healed far faster and experienced less issues after surgery than those who did not [6]. Likewise, in a meta-analysis from 2020 attested to the effectiveness of mastoid obliteration in lowering surgical morbidity and enhancing general patient outcomes [7]. Notwithstanding these developments,

there is still disagreement over the long-term advantages and possible hazards of MCO in clinical practice [8]. This study aims to compare the healing time and postoperative outcomes between patients undergoing MRM with and without MCO.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a multicentric, prospective, observational study.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over six months, including patient recruitment, surgery, follow-up, and data analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted across multiple tertiary care centers, ensuring a diverse patient population. Each center followed a standardized protocol to maintain consistency in procedures and data collection.

Participants: A total of 104 participants were included in the study. Participants were patients scheduled to undergo MRM, with or without MCO during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18-65 years.
- Patients diagnosed with chronic suppurative otitis media requiring MRM.
- Patients consenting to participate in the study.
- Patients who were medically fit for surgery.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of previous ear surgery.
- Patients with systemic conditions that could affect wound healing (e.g., diabetes, immunocompromised states).
- Patients who were lost to follow-up.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited consecutively from all eligible patients during the study period. Performance bias was reduced by standardizing the surgical procedures and postoperative care across all centers. Detection bias was addressed by blinding the outcome assessors to the type of surgery (with or without obliteration) the patient underwent.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a standardized data collection form. Information recorded included patient demographics, medical history, details of the surgical procedure, and postoperative outcomes, specifically focusing on healing time. Healing time was defined as the period from the day of surgery to the complete epithelisation of the mastoid cavity.

Procedure: All surgeries were performed by experienced otologic surgeons following the same surgical protocol. Patients were randomly assigned to either undergo MRM with or without MCO. Postoperative care was standardized, and follow-up visits were scheduled at regular intervals until complete healing was achieved.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized baseline characteristics, and healing times between groups were compared using an independent samples t-test with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. Multivariate regression analysis adjusted for potential confounders.

Results

A total of 104 participants were enrolled in the study, with 52 patients in the MRM with MCO group (Group A) and 52 in the MRM without MCO group (Group B).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Group A (n=52)	Group B (n=52)	p-value
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	42.3 $\pm$ 10.2	43.1 $\pm$ 9.8	0.65
Gender (Male/Female)	28/24	30/22	0.67
Duration of Disease (years)	7.5 $\pm$ 3.2	7.7 $\pm$ 3.4	0.75
Smoking Status (Yes/No)	15/37	17/35	0.68
Comorbidities (Yes/No)	12/40	10/42	0.63

No significant differences were observed between the two groups in terms of age, gender distribution, duration of disease, smoking status, or presence of comorbidities ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons).

Healing Time

The primary outcome of the study was the comparison of healing times between the two

groups. The mean healing time in Group A (with obliteration) was 6.8 weeks ($\pm$ 1.5 weeks), whereas in Group B (without obliteration), the mean healing time was 9.2 weeks ($\pm$ 2.1 weeks). The difference in healing times between the two groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that patients who underwent MCO had a faster healing process compared to those who did not.

Table 2: Comparison of Healing Time between Groups

Group	Mean Healing Time (weeks)	Standard Deviation (SD)	p-value
Group A	6.8	1.5	< 0.001
Group B	9.2	2.1	

To account for potential confounding factors such as age, gender, smoking status, and comorbidities, a multivariate regression analysis was conducted. The analysis confirmed that MCO was an independent predictor of reduced healing time, with an adjusted p-value of < 0.001.

Table 3: Multivariate Regression Analysis for Healing Time

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error (SE)	p-value
MCO (Yes/No)	-2.4	0.5	< 0.001
Age	0.02	0.03	0.41
Gender (Male/Female)	0.1	0.4	0.81
Smoking Status (Yes/No)	0.3	0.5	0.58
Comorbidities (Yes/No)	0.5	0.6	0.48

The negative coefficient for MCO indicates that it is associated with a reduction in healing time, independent of other variables included in the model.

Secondary Outcomes: Secondary outcomes included the incidence of postoperative

complications such as infection, granulation tissue formation, and the need for revision surgery. The incidence of complications was lower in Group A (10%) compared to Group B (17%), though this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.22$).

Table 4: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Group A (n=52)	Group B (n=52)	p-value
Infection	3 (5.8%)	6 (11.5%)	0.29
Granulation Tissue Formation	2 (3.8%)	4 (7.7%)	0.41
Need for Revision Surgery	0 (0%)	1 (1.9%)	0.31

Although not statistically significant, the trend suggests a lower complication rate in patients who underwent mastoid cavity obliteration.

Summary of Findings

- **Healing Time:** Significantly faster in the obliteration group (6.8 weeks vs. 9.2 weeks, $p < 0.001$).
- **Complications:** Lower but not statistically significant in the obliteration group.
- **Regression Analysis:** MCO was an independent predictor of reduced healing time.

These findings suggest that MCO is associated with faster healing times and may contribute to a lower incidence of postoperative complications, although the latter requires further study for statistical significance.

Discussion

The primary outcome of the study was healing time, defined as the duration from surgery to complete epithelization of the mastoid cavity. The results demonstrated that Group A, the obliteration group, had a significantly faster healing time, with an average of 6.8 weeks compared to 9.2 weeks in Group B. This difference was highly significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that MCO effectively reduces the time required for healing after surgery.

Further analysis through multivariate regression confirmed that MCO was an independent predictor of reduced healing time, even after adjusting for potential confounders such as age, gender, smoking status, and comorbidities. This suggests that the faster healing observed in Group A was directly attributable to the obliteration procedure rather than other patient-related factors.

Secondary outcomes, including the incidence of postoperative complications such as infections, granulation tissue formation, and the need for revision surgery, were also assessed. Although Group A exhibited a lower complication rate (10% compared to 17% in Group B), the differences were not statistically significant. However, the trend suggests a potential benefit of MCO in reducing postoperative complications, warranting further research to confirm these findings.

A research conducted wherein patients having MRM with and without MCO had their recovery periods compared. It was discovered that patients who had their mastoid cavities destroyed recovered more quickly, taking an average of 10.67 weeks to heal as opposed to 12.47 weeks for individuals who did not. The statistical significance of this difference underscores the potential advantages of cavity obliteration in shortening the healing period [10].

A study carried out where a comparison research comparing patients who underwent MCO and those who had open mastoid cavities, with an emphasis on the quality of life and surgical results. According to the study, individuals who had their cavities completely removed had much less side effects, including discomfort, discharge, and light headedness. Furthermore, at three months after surgery, quicker epithelialisation showed that the destroyed group's cavity had healed more effectively [11].

In a similar way, in a research it was examined that the results of MCO utilising a vascularised periosteal-temporofascial swing flap. Three weeks after surgery, the data showed that destroyed cavities had superior outcomes in terms of epithelialisation and discharge status. Furthermore, at six months, these patients' hearing results were better, indicating that cavity obliteration could also help with auditory rehabilitation [12].

Conclusion

The study provides strong evidence that Mastoid Cavity Obliteration MCO significantly accelerates healing time following MRM. While the reduction in complications was not statistically significant, the overall trend favors obliteration. These findings support the incorporation of MCO into standard surgical practice for eligible patients to promote faster recovery and potentially reduce postoperative complications.

References

1. Acuin J. Chronic suppurative otitis media. *BMJ Clin Evid.* 2018.
2. Monasta L, Ronfani L, Marchetti F, Montico M, Vecchi Brumatti L, Bavcar A, et al. Burden of disease caused by otitis media: Systematic review and global estimates. *PLoS One.* 2019; 7(4).
3. Browning GG, Merchant SN, Kelly G, Swan IR, Canter R, McKerrow WS. Chronic otitis media. In: Gleeson M, Browning GG, editors. *Scott-Brown's Otorhinolaryngology, Head and Neck Surgery.* 8th ed. London: Hodder Arnold; 2018. p. 3395-445.
4. Sweeney AD, Hunter JB, O'Connell BP, Bennett ML, Wanna GB, Haynes DS. Management of the mastoid cavity: Update on obliteration. *Curr Opin Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2019; 27(5):351-7.
5. Howard BE, Hansberger S, Shah MD, Shelton C. Autologous materials for mastoid obliteration: A review. *Laryngoscope.* 2020;130(3): 697-703.
6. Lin YC, Wang WH, Weng HC, Ho KY, Tseng CC. Comparison of outcomes for canal wall down mastoidectomy with or without mastoid obliteration. *Am J Otolaryngol.* 2019;40(1):42-6.
7. Gurgel RK, Jackler RK, Dobie RA, Popelka GR. A systematic review of outcomes following mastoid obliteration. *Otol Neurotol.* 2020; 41(2):137-44.
8. Penido ND, Borin A, Iha LC, Yoshinari HH. Mastoid obliteration in the management of chronic otitis media. *Int Arch Otorhinolaryngol.* 2020;24(2)
9. Kurien G, Greeff K, Gomaa N, Ho A, Shea C. Mastoidectomy and the middle ear risk index. *J Laryngol Otol.* 2021;135(3):244-8.
10. Tulachan B. Comparison of Healing Time Following Modified Radical Mastoidectomy with or without Mastoid Cavity Obliteration. 2018.
11. Maheshwari S, Kumar R, Nagle S. Comparative study of quality of life and surgical outcome in open mastoid cavity and mastoid cavity obliteration in canal wall down mastoidectomy. *Int J Otorhinolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2023.
12. V. R., Bhardwaj R, Uddin S, et al. Modified Radical Mastoidectomy: Open Mastoid Cavity versus Cavity Obliteration Using Periosteal Temporofascial Flap - A Comparative Study. *Bengal J Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2022.